

TAXATION OF DIGITAL ACTIVITIES: AN EVALUATION OF THE NIGERIAN

APPROACH IN A GLOBAL CONTEXT*

The digital market, having grown to be one of the most lucrative globally, has prompted the desires of governments across the world to tax the profit that emerges from their territory because of these digital activities. However, due to the lack of physical presence¹ of the Non-Resident Companies² (being the major suppliers of digital services in Nigeria³), taxation of the said activities have proven difficult. Being a key factor necessitating the shift from the old regime of taxing NRCs under section 13 of Companies Income Tax Act (“CITA”), to the enactment of the Finance Act 2019⁴ which came into force on 13 January 2020.

Section 13 of CITA did not expressly provide for the physical presence requirement to tax NRCs. However, such an interpretation could be inferred from section 13(2)(a) of CITA requiring a “*fixed base*”. This argument is supported by the court’s decision in *Addax Petroleum Services Ltd v. Federal Inland Revenue Service*⁵ “... any significant territorial connection to Nigeria will suffice if the Nigerian location is a place of regular resort for the foreign company for business purposes...” The NRCs took advantage of this provision by employing digital means to provide digital products and services, hence not requiring an agent to conduct business for them, neither did they require the maintenance of stock from which deliveries are made.

A report released by the *Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission* in 2018, showed the degree to which the Nigerian government had been robbed of tax in the digital space. It was stated in the report that the digital economy of Nigeria is expected to generate \$88 billion and create three

* Joel Odili. Joelodili7@gmail.com

¹ Physical Presence requirement was the hallmark of the Companies Income Tax Act Cap. C21 L.F.N. 2004 (as amended), s. 13.

² Herein after known as “NRCs”.

³ Such as; Google, Twitter, Netflix, Facebook, Amazon, Asos, among others.

⁴ As an amendment to certain CITA provisions.

⁵ (2013) 9 TLRN 126.

million new jobs by the end of 2021⁶. This uncovering led to the introduction of the *Significant Economic Presence* (“SEP”) principle to tax NRCs under the Finance Act, as opposed to physical presence⁷. The formulation of SEP is attributed to the *Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development* (“OECD”) *Base Erosion and Profit Shifting* (“BEPS”) Action Plan⁸. However, the mode of its application varies from country to country based on the options presented by the OECD⁹. These options include; the revenue-based factor¹⁰, digital-based factor¹¹, user-based factor¹².

Under the Finance Act¹³, the profits of NRCs is made subject to Company Income Tax in Nigeria where it *transmits, emits or receives signals, sounds, messages, images or data of any kind by cable, radio, electromagnetic systems or any other electronic or wireless apparatus to Nigeria in respect of any activity, including electronic commerce, application store, high frequency trading, electronic data storage, online adverts, participative network platform, online payments and so on, to the extent that the company has significant economic presence in Nigeria and profit can be attributable to such activity*¹⁴. The scope of SEP under the act¹⁵ extends to the *furnishing of technical, management, consultancy or professional services* outside of Nigeria to a person resident in Nigeria. However, unlike the former, this provision does not directly relate to digital activities, albeit worthy of mention.

⁶ O. Isiadinso and E. Omoju, ‘Taxation Of Nigeria's Digital Economy: Challenges And Prospects’. (2019). <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/tax-authorities/810276/taxation-of-nigeria39s-digital-economy-challenges-and-prospects?type=mondaqai&score=76>> accessed 26 August, 2020.

⁷ Finance Act 2019, s. 13(2)(c).

⁸ In a bid to ensure that digital activities are taxed in European Union countries.

⁹ Final Report on Addressing the Tax Challenges of the Digital Economy, Chapter VII, OECD Action 1, 2015 para. 277, p. 107. Available online at: <<https://www.oecd.org/tax/addressing-the-tax-challenges-of-the-digital-economy-action-1-2015-final-report9789264241046-en.htm>>.

¹⁰ SEP determined using the revenue generated by customers in Nigeria.

¹¹ SEP determined based a company’s digital presence.

¹² SEP determined based on the user base of an enterprise and its related data.

¹³ Finance Act 2019, s. 4(a)(ii).

¹⁴ Emphasis added.

¹⁵ Finance Act 2019, s. 4(b).

The Act does not define SEP, but requires the Minister of Finance by an Order, to determine what constitutes SEP¹⁶. This provision accommodates future changes and advancement in the business world, though it breeds uncertainty.

The Minister of Finance, Budget and Economic Planning, *Zainab Shamsuna Ahmed*, on 29 May 2020, issued the **Companies Income Tax (Significant Economic Presence) Order, 2020** which outlined the scope of SEP in Nigeria¹⁷. The Order made a distinction between NRCs providing digital services and those that provide services that are not necessarily digital. The SEP scope for digital NRCs can be categorized into three:

- 1) If the foreign company in an accounting year, derives gross income equal to or greater than N25,000,000 (or its equivalence in foreign currency), from any combination of the following:
 - Streaming, or downloading services of digital contents to any person in Nigeria;
 - Transmission of data collected about Nigerian users generated from users' digital activity;
 - Provision of goods or services directly or indirectly to Nigerians through digital platforms;
 - Provision of intermediation services through digital platforms that link suppliers and customers in Nigeria.
- 2) The use of a Nigerian domain name (.ng) or registration of a website in Nigeria.
- 3) Having a purposeful and sustained interaction with persons in Nigeria by customizing its digital page or platform to target persons in Nigeria, including reflecting the prices of its

¹⁶ *Ibid*, s. 4(c).

¹⁷ The order is operative from the 3rd of February, 2020.

products or services in Nigerian currency or providing options for billing or payment in Nigerian currency.

The Order provides that, where there exists a multilateral or consensus agreement to address the tax challenges arising from the digitalization of the economy, such agreement would override the relevant provisions in CITA that relate to SEP.

The 25 million naira threshold provided for in the Order affects only the first category. It is also observed that the SEP scope for digital NRCs, embraces the factors presented by OECD's report which was earlier mentioned in this paper. Nations like Israel and India have applied the SEP principle in like manner¹⁸. In Israel, SEP of NRCs is determined based on the following: Online contract conclusion between NRCs and customers in Israel; Use of the digital products and services by large number of Israeli customers; Localised features on the web site of the NRC; The NRC generating significant revenue closely related to the volume of online activities performed by users in Israel¹⁹. In India, there are two thresholds for SEP of NRCs, namely; 1) Based on local revenue and 2) Based on the number of local users²⁰.

The Order requires NRCs that have SEP to register income taxes and prepare financial statements for their Nigerian income²¹. Banks and other authorized agents would be employed by the Federal

¹⁸ OECD (2018), "Relevant tax policy developments", in *Tax Challenges Arising from Digitalisation – Interim Report 2018: Inclusive Framework on BEPS*, OECD Publishing, Paris, < <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264293083-6-en>> accessed on 1 August, 2020.

¹⁹ Administrative Circular No. 04/2016 (11 April 2016) released to clarify the circumstances in which a foreign enterprise engaged in online activities may be liable to corporate income tax in Israel.

²⁰ Union Budget 2018, Amendment to the Income Tax Act of 1961, s. 9(1).

²¹ **Section 55 of CITA** requires NRCs to file tax return in Nigeria.

Inland Revenue Service²² to act as collecting agents of outstanding tax liabilities imposed by the SEP framework²³.

Obvious implementation issues are arising from the Order. One of such is the need to renegotiate tax treaties between Nigeria and other countries because those treaties were founded on *permanent establishment* as the basis for taxation. Also, the 25 million Naira as a threshold is too low given other currencies of higher value (e.g., dollar, pound). The instability of the Naira is likely to disrupt the enforcement of SEP principle.

How willing would NRCs be to submit relevant data to FIRS?²⁴ Countries like the United States where digital companies are residents have refrained from taxing digital activities, and to protect those companies, they impose stiff tariffs on countries intending to tax their digital activities.

Conclusively, there is no doubt that guidelines need to be put in place to give full effect to the SEP principle. Taxation of NRCs based on SEP is still a work in progress, as it requires expert knowledge of information analysis for establishing tax liability. The cost of implementation has raised questions as to whether this venture is worthwhile, given that advanced nations that tax digital activities receive insignificant tax return from their digital market, when considered alongside the broader tax landscape of the country.

²² Herein after known as “FIRS”.

²³ O. Oluwole, ‘Digital Taxes, Significant Economic Presence And Tax Implications In Nigeria’. (2020). <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/transfer-pricing/971838/digital-taxes-significant-economic-presence-and-tax-implications-in-nigeria?type=popular&signup=true>> accessed 1 August, 2020.

²⁴ The FIRS may need to rely on data gathered from Country by Country Reports filed under the Income Tax (Country by Country Reporting) Regulations, 2018 and through collaboration with tax authorities in other jurisdictions.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Final Report on Addressing the Tax Challenges of the Digital Economy, Chapter VII, OECD Action 1, 2015 para. 277, p. 107. Available online at: <<https://www.oecd.org/tax/addressing-the-tax-challenges-of-the-digital-economy-action-1-2015-final-report9789264241046-en.htm>>.

O. Isiadinso and E. Omoju, 'Taxation Of Nigeria's Digital Economy: Challenges And Prospects'. (2019). <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/tax-authorities/810276/taxation-of-nigeria39s-digital-economy-challenges-and-prospects?type=mondaqai&score=76>> accessed 26 August, 2020.

O. Oluwole, 'Digital Taxes, Significant Economic Presence And Tax Implications In Nigeria'. (2020). <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/transfer-pricing/971838/digital-taxes-significant-economic-presence-and-tax-implications-in-nigeria?type=popular&signup=true>> accessed 1 August, 2020.

OECD (2018), "Relevant tax policy developments", in *Tax Challenges Arising from Digitalisation – Interim Report 2018: Inclusive Framework on BEPS*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <<https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264293083-6-en>> accessed on 1 August, 2020.